

Reactivity of the Methylene group in Coumarin-4-acetic acids.

Part II.

Condensation with aromatic aldehydes to coumaryl phenyl ethylenes.

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It has been shown (J. Ind. Chem. Soc., Vol. I, 107) that coumarin-4-acetic acids and their ethyl esters condense with salicylaldehyde, to form a new class of bodies which have been named 4:3'-dicoumaryls. The study of this reaction has now been extended to other aromatic aldehydes, and in a few cases the parallel condensations with phenyl-acetic acid have also been examined. The products are of the stilbene type in which one of the phenyl groups has been replaced by the coumarin nucleus, the latter being attached at the 4-position to the ethylene carbon atom. The reactions proceed thus:

The carboxylic acids (I) frequently split off carbon dioxide during the reaction giving the free ethylene derivatives (II), and this is found to happen much more readily if the experiment is carried out under the conditions of Knoevenagel's reaction than by Perkin's method.

The nature of the product ultimately obtained, however, depends largely on the stability of the acids (I) at the temperature of the experiment. Thus, the product obtained from vanillin and phenylacetic acid by heating at 140° in the presence of piperidine was found to consist mainly of the free ethylene derivative (II), whilst piperonal under the same conditions and at a considerably higher temperature (170°), gave chiefly the carboxylic acid (I), and only a minute quantity of the CO₂-free product. Coumarin-4-acetic acids, as a class, split off carbon dioxide completely at their melting points (Dey, T., 1915, 107, 1610), and this decomposition is found in some cases to have begun at a much lower temperature. The instability of these acids, therefore, constituted a serious obstacle to the progress of this work. As the reaction depended solely on the presence of the methylene group in the acid, it could obviously not proceed at all if carbon dioxide were split off prior to the condensation. Attempts to stabilise the carboxyl-group by esterification did not lead to the desired result as the curious fact came to light that the esters were remarkably unreactive bodies and would not condense at all with aldehydes in the presence of piperidine, although under exactly the same conditions they gave with salicylaldehyde an almost quantitative yield of the 4:3'-dicoumaryls (*loc. cit.*). We cannot say we have been very successful in our attempts to solve the problem of controlling the process so that the decomposition of the acids to the 4-methyl-pyrone would be reduced to a minimum and this condensation with aldehydes to the coumaryl-phenyl-ethylene raised to a maximum, but as a general rule, satisfactory results were obtained only when the temperature was maintained as far below the fusion points of the acids as was compatible with the initiation of the reaction. Even then the formation of considerable amount of the pyrone could not

be avoided, and its separation was found to be much more difficult than could be anticipated.

Attention was next directed towards effecting the condensation with such aldehydes as would permit of the products being separated chemically from the corresponding 4-methyl-pyrones. Thus vanillin and *p*-dimethyl-amino-benzaldehyde condensed with coumarin-4-acetic acids to form the corresponding *p*-hydroxy, and *p*-dimethyl-amino-phenyl-coumaryl ethylene derivatives respectively which could be readily purified by extracting with cold dilute alkalis or acids.

The product from vanillin and 7-methyl-coumarin-4-acetic acid seems to be of some interest on account of the remarkable colour changes which it undergoes in alkaline solution. The compound, which has a bright yellow colour, dissolves in cold dilute caustic alkalis with a deep red colour, and on acidification, the original substance is precipitated unchanged. If, however, the alkaline solution be allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature (30°C), the colour gradually fades, and in the course of about half an hour the deep red solution becomes practically colourless. The same change is found to occur in about a minute, if the solution be warmed in the water-bath. On cooling and acidifying this solution, a milky emulsion is produced which dissolves immediately in cold dilute sodium carbonate to a clear colourless solution. On standing, however, at the ordinary temperature or even at 0°, the emulsion slowly changes into yellow crystals of the original substance, which then dissolves in dilute caustic soda with the same deep red colour as was observed before. The change of the emulsion into the yellow solid is greatly accelerated by warming.

The interesting point that emerges out of a study of this cycle of changes is that the milky solid obtained by

perceptible change either on standing or boiling the solution.

These experiments, therefore, furnish clear evidence in favour of the idea that the changes in colour are caused by the opening of the pyrone ring for which the presence of water or alcohol is indispensable: in dry benzene no change in colour takes place. Attempts are now being made to synthesise and study more closely other compounds of a similar type with a view to throw further light on this question.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A. COUMARYL-PHENYL-ETHYLENES.

7-methyl-4-coumaryl-p-methoxy phenyl-ethylene.

2.8 Grams of freshly distilled anisaldehyde and 4 grams of pure 7-methyl-coumarin-4-acetic acid were mixed in a small flask, 8-10 drops of piperidine added, and the mixture heated in an oil-bath at 130°-135° under air reflux for four hours. On cooling, the solid mass was extracted several times with small amounts of hot rectified spirit, and the yellowish residue crystallised once from acetic acid and then from absolute alcohol. Pale yellow needles were obtained melting at 180°, and dissolving in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep red colour in the characteristic manner of the stilbenes (Found: C=78.50; H=5.62. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C=78.08; H=5.48 per cent.)

α -naphthapyrone-4-p-methoxyphenyl ethylene.

This was prepared in the usual way from anisaldehyde (2.5 grams) and α -naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid (4 grams) by heating to 125°-130° for three hours. The brownish residue left after washing the dark product with alcohol, when recrystallised twice from boiling glacial acetic acid,

formed bright yellow needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 182° - 83° C. It gave the usual red colour with strong sulphuric acid, and readily decolourised a solution of bromine in chloroform. (Found: C=80.14; H=4.48. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2$, requires C=80.48; H=4.87 per cent.)

7-methyl-4-coumaryl-3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxy phenyl ethylene.

Vanillin (3 grams), and 7-methyl-coumarin acetic acid (4 grams) were heated in the usual way for 3-4 hours at 140° , the hot melt transferred to a dish and washed three times with 10 c.c. of cold methylated spirit. The residue was then extracted with cold decinormal caustic soda and the dark red filtrate acidified. A dark gummy mass was precipitated, which on rubbing with a little cold alcohol, changed into a hard crystalline powder. Two crystallisations from fifty per cent. acetic acid gave golden yellow needles melting sharply at 222° . (Found: C=74.52; H=5.48. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$, requires C=74.02; H=5.19 per cent.)

An account of the remarkable colour changes which this substance undergoes in alkaline solution has been given in the introduction.

7-Methyl-4-coumaryl-p-dimethylamino-phenyl ethylene.

This was prepared in the usual way by heating *p*-dimethyl-aminobenzaldehyde (3 grams), and 7-methyl-coumarin-acetic acid (4 grams) with piperidine for 4-5 hours at 140° - 150° . The product was purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold, and reprecipitating with ammonia. Recrystallised from alcohol or acetic acid, it came down in beautiful orange-coloured needles which melted to a dark red liquid at 190° . Its solution in mineral acids is colourless.

(Found : C=78.32; H=6.61. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C=78.69; H=6.23 per cent.)

A yellow crystalline *picrate* is precipitated on addition of aqueous picric acid to a hot alcoholic solution of the compound. It turned red and melted at 204° and then decomposed with a small explosion.

The following *salts* were prepared by adding the reagents to a solution of the base in dilute hydrochloric acid :—

The *mercurichloride* separated in colourless prisms which were moderately soluble in hot water.

The *dichromate* came down as a chocolate brown precipitate which decomposed on boiling with water.

The *platinichloride* formed a pale yellow precipitate.

The *ferrocyanide* was precipitated as a light green crystalline powder.

α -naphthapyrone-4-p-dimethylaminophenyl ethylene.

This was prepared from the aldehyde (2.5 grams) α -naphthacoumarin acetic acid (4 grams) and piperidine by heating to 140° for a couple of hours. The product was purified as in the preceding case, and then crystallised twice from hot absolute alcohol. Deep red prisms were deposited melting at 215° - 216° . The yield was poor amounting to only 0.6 grams. (Found: C=81.30; H=5.73. $C_{23}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C=80.94; H=5.57 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* is sparingly soluble, and crystallises from hot concentrated solutions in colourless needles. On diluting the solution with water, the compound gradually dissociates into the free base which comes down as a red precipitate. (Found: Cl=10.24. $C_{23}H_{19}O_2N, HCl$ requires Cl=9.4 per cent.)

B. SUBSTITUTED STILBENES AND STILBENE
CARBOXYLIC ACIDS.

4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-stilbene- α' -carboxylic acid

Vanillin (2 grams), sodium phenyl acetate (6 grams) and acetic anhydride (15 c. c.) were boiled under reflux for six hours, and the product poured into water and boiled to decompose the excess of acetic anhydride. An oil was precipitated which, on standing overnight, completely solidified. The solid was powdered and digested for an hour with cold sodium carbonate when most of it dissolved leaving a small amount of a white residue which was found to be acetyl vanillin. The solution was acidified and the precipitate redissolved in 2N caustic soda and boiled in order to decompose the acetyl derivative simultaneously formed. On acidifying the cold solution a colourless solid was deposited which was found to be pure after one crystallisation from alcohol. It formed colourless rectangular plates sintering at 181° and melting at 186°-87°. Its solutions in alkalis or alkali carbonates are colourless.

(Found: C=71.34; H=5.38. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C=71.11; H=5.18 per cent.)

4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-stilbene, was the sole product isolated on heating vanillin (5.5 grams), phenyl acetic acid (5 grams) and piperidine to 140°-150° for four hours. The solid obtained on pouring into water was washed with alcohol and sodium carbonate, and the residue crystallised twice from alcohol. Glistening leaflets melting at 134° were obtained, which slowly went into solution when treated with cold sodium hydroxide (2N). The solution had a pale yellow tint, and on dilution, exhibited a blue fluorescence. It was insoluble in sodium carbonate.

(Found: C = 79.21; H = 6.02. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2$ requires C = 79.64; H = 6.19 per cent.)

3: 4-Dimethoxy stilbene obtained by methylating the above compound crystallised from alcohol in soft colourless needles melting at 111°.

(Found: C = 80.31; H = 6.90. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C = 80.00; H = 6.66 per cent.)

5-Bromo-4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-stilbene- α' -carboxylic acid prepared by Perkin's method from 5-bromo-vanillin (7 grams), sodium phenyl acetate (4 grams) and acetic anhydride (15 c. c.) separated from alcohol in colourless foliated crystals melting at 222°. It dissolved in cold sodium carbonate to a colourless solution.

(Found: Br = 22.95. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4Br$ requires Br = 22.92 per cent.)

4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-2': 4'-dinitro-stilbene.

Vanillin (5 grams), meta-dinitro-toluene (6 grams) and piperidine were heated to 150°.160° for two hours, and the dark melt transferred to a dish where it solidified on cooling. The solid was powdered, washed carefully with small amounts of cold alcohol, and then crystallised twice from boiling glacial acetic acid. Deep red oblong plates m.p. 193° were obtained, weighing nearly 2 grams.

(Found: C = 57.41; H = 3.98. $C_{18}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires C = 56.96; H = 3.80 per cent.)

The substance turns black immediately on the addition of dilute alkalis and on warming, slowly goes into solution with a dark brown colour. On acidifying the solution the original red substance is reprecipitated.

p-Dimethylamino stilbene, prepared by heating a mixture of phenyl acetic acid (4 grams), p-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde (3.3 grams) and piperidine at 160° for three hours, crystallised from alcohol in colourless

broad glistening leaflets melting at 150°. The same compound appears to have been synthesised by Sachs and Sachs (Ber. 1905, 38, 51) by treating *p*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde with magnesium benzyl chloride and heating the carbinol obtained under 10 mm. pressure. It forms a sparingly soluble hydrochloride (m.p. 174°) which dissolves in a large excess of water without appreciable dissociation.

(Found: N=6.49. $C_{16}H_{17}N$ requires N=6.28 per cent.)

Methylene ether of 3:4-dihydroxy stilbens- α' -carboxylic acid.

Piperonal (4.5 grams) sodium phenyl acetate (5 grams), and acetic anhydride (12 grams) were heated to 150°-160° for six hours. The product was poured into water, boiled, and the solid extracted with cold sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitated with acids. Crystallisation from alcohol gave colourless prisms melting at 231°-32°. The white *silver salt* was analysed.

(Found: Ag=28.31. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4Ag$ requires Ag=28.80 per cent.)

The *ethyl ester*, prepared by treating the silver salt with ethyl iodide in dry benzene, crystallised in hard rhombic prisms melting at 104°.

(Found: C=72.74; H=5.48. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C=72.97; H=5.40 per cent.)

Methylene ether of 3:4-dihydroxy stilbene

Phenyl acetic acid, piperonal and piperidine were heated for six hours at 170° and the product washed with cold alcohol and then digested with sodium carbonate solution when most of it dissolved. In acidifying the alkaline solution and crystallising the resulting precipitate from alcohol, colourless prisms (m.p. 232°) of the stilbene carboxylic acid were obtained. The residue which

weighed about 0.3 grams was washed with a little dilute sodium Hydroxide and then crystallised from alcohol when beautiful shining needles appeared, m.p. 95° - 96° . (Found: C=79.96; H=5.05. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C=80.35; H=5.35 per cent.) It readily formed a *dibromide* which came down from benzene in small white crystals melting at 187° . The compound is evidently identical with the stilbene prepared by Hell and Wiegandt (Ber. 1904, 37, 1431-32) by condensing benzyl magnesium chloride with piperonal and then distilling the product.

Methylene ether of 3 : 4-dihydroxy-2 : 4'-dinitro-stilbene.

Piperonal (5 grams), and *meta*-dinitro-toluene (6 grams) were heated with piperidine at 150° for about two hours, and the product worked up in the usual way. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid, it came down in reddish brown plates melting at 183° .

(Found: N=9.37. $C_{15}H_{10}O_8N_2$ requires N=8.92 per cent.)

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